

COMPLICATIONS AND METHODS OF THEIR ELIMINATION IN BRIDGE PROSTHETICS SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS

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Abstract

At present, extensive clinical experience has been accumulated in the use of dental implants for prosthetic restoration of various defects in the dentition. The success of dental implantation depends on a number of factors, both surgical and orthopedic. One of the orthopedic factors affecting the treatment outcome is the condition of the occlusal relationships [6]. In this regard, the alignment of the occlusal relationships of teeth supported by implants with adjacent teeth and antagonist teeth is of particular importance to avoid excessive localized functional loads on the implant, which lead to instability of the implant-bone connection area.

Keywords: implant-supported bridge prostheses, grinding, osseointegration of peri-implant tissues

A necessary condition for the dynamic remodeling of cortical and cancellous bone tissue is the correct and even distribution of mechanical load during chewing, taking into account its magnitude and direction. However, the osseointegration of implants and the long-term preservation of a stable implant-bone interface, capable of withstanding significant chewing loads, especially in patients with various occlusal disorders leading to the formation of traumatic nodes, remains a relevant problem [5,7].

Objective of the Study

To examine the significance of occlusal correction through selective grinding on the osseointegration processes of peri-implant tissues.

Materials and Methods

Clinical and radiological studies were conducted at various stages of prosthetic treatment using dental implants in three groups of patients: Group 1: 8 patients using implant-supported bridge prostheses; group 2: 10 patients with single artificial crowns on implants; group 3: 13 patients using metal-ceramic bridge prostheses supported by devitalized teeth and implants.

Patients in Group 3 did not undergo selective occlusal grinding.

Selective occlusal grinding was performed in 12 stages (Bushan M.G., Kalamkarov Kh.A., 1983): In distal occlusion (static phase). During the reverse movement of the mandible to the position of central occlusion (static phase). In central occlusion (static phase). In anterior occlusion (static phase). During the forward movement of the mandible from central occlusion to anterior occlusion (dynamic phase). In lateral occlusion (right and left) on the balancing side. During the movement of the mandible from central occlusion to transverse occlusion. In lateral occlusion on the working side. During the movement of the mandible from central occlusion to transverse occlusion on the working side. Elimination of supracontacts of canines in lateral occlusion (static phase). Elimination of supracontacts in other areas of the dentition.

Smoothing and polishing of all ground tooth surfaces.

During selective grinding, traumatic cusps were identified using articulating paper. Premature contacts were corrected in limited areas of the enamel, on cusp slopes, to minimize trauma to the superficial enamel layers. After each manipulation, the teeth were coated with fluoride varnish from the company Belak-F.

All patients were advised to brush their teeth twice a day with toothpaste that prevents increased enamel sensitivity during the period of selective occlusal grinding. Upon completion of the selective grinding, the enamel was polished with fluoride-containing pastes to achieve an absolutely smooth surface. This procedure was performed to prevent excessive plaque accumulation.

The process of osseointegration of peri-implant bone tissues was monitored using targeted radiography [7,8].

Study Results

During clinical examinations, patients exhibited signs of occlusal disorders, specifically:

Traumatic occlusion, manifested by more pronounced exposure of the necks and roots of certain teeth. Increased tooth mobility (Grade I-II) in the area of occlusal trauma. Uneven deepening of peri-implant sulci in 7 patients. Peri-implant sulcus depth, measured through probing from vestibular, oral, mesial, and distal aspects, was increased in 4 patients.

The examinations were conducted before the start of selective occlusal grinding, upon completion of all stages, and one month after grinding. The grinding was performed in stages, every 2-3 days, allowing the patient to gradually adapt to changes in occlusion.

The effectiveness of selective grinding of pronounced cusps of preserved teeth, as well as occlusal surfaces of dental prostheses supported by implants, was monitored over 1, 2, and 3 months using radiography. Special attention was paid to the degree of bone

tissue atrophy in the implant area and the radiographic density of bone tissue in the region of the implants.

Radiological Findings

Radiological examination showed that in patients from Groups 1 and 2, who underwent selective grinding of occlusal surfaces, there was bone regrowth along the contour of the implant threads within one month after implantation. No signs of inflammation were observed. The selective grinding was continuously performed according to the described method during the first week of wearing dental prostheses.

On X-ray images taken after 3 months, bone tissue had acquired sufficient density and surrounded the threaded portion of the implant. By 6 months, bone tissue fully enveloped the implant from all sides.

Patients in Group 3, who did not undergo selective grinding, showed: A decrease in the height of the cortical bone shadow in the lower jaw. Reduced radiographic bone density in the peri-implant area. Clinically, this was expressed as swelling, edema, and deepening of the peri-implant sulcus, along with bleeding.

More detailed radiological studies revealed progressive loss of alveolar bone in the peri-implant region in the early stages. By 3 months, radiographs in Group 3 showed delayed osseointegration with the formation of fibrous encapsulation around implants.

Long-Term Radiological Findings

A fragment of an orthopantomogram 3 months after the placement of two-stage screw implants showed bone tissue surrounding the intraosseous elements without significant signs of resorption.

However, a fragment of an orthopantomogram of the same patient 1.5 years after prosthetic treatment showed: Bone resorption in the peri-implant area, forming bone pockets 1-2 mm deep. Reduction in bone density around the implants.

A comparative assessment of radiological parameters in the peri-implant area among Group 3 patients confirmed the necessity and validity of functional relief of the implant-prosthesis system through selective occlusal grinding of prosthetic occlusal surfaces and antagonist teeth.

Additionally, the observed delay in osseointegration supports the established view that the success of dental implant integration is closely related to occlusal relationships. Excessive functional overload of the implant-prosthesis-bone complex triggers the disorgan-

ization and resorption of structural bone units, particularly trabeculae, forming cavities filled with fibrous connective tissue [8].

Due to further bone resorption and its degeneration into non-mineralized osteoid tissue, trabecular and osteonal microfractures are possible [9].

Conclusion

Thus, timely and targeted selective occlusal grinding prevents the development of metabolic, functional, and structural changes in the peri-implant alveolar bone. This significantly improves the prognosis of orthopedic treatment in patients with dental implants.

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